

Electrochemical Studies of Carbamazepine

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Electrochemical investigations of carbamazepine (1) are carried out by cyclic voltammetry, differential pulse polarography and coulometry. The compound undergoes a quasi-reversible two-electron reduction process at the 10,11 C=C of the heterocyclic ring. The cathodic shift in the E_{pc} as pH is increased, indicates the involvement of hydrogen ions in the redox process. A plausible EC mechanism is suggested for the pH and scan rate dependent CV profiles. The mechanism is supported by electronic spectroscopy and coulometry. The diffusion coefficients and conformational isomerisation (following-reaction) rate constants are calculated based on Nicholson and Shain method. An analytical technique in differential pulse polarography is developed for the assaying of carbamazepine in various commercial drug formulations.

Carbamazepine (1), which is 5H-dibenz[*b,f*]-azepine-5-carboxamide and commercially available as Tegretol, Carpatol, Carmaz etc., is a tricyclic iminostilbene (*cis*) based compound with structural resemblance to the anti-depressant drug, imipramine. Carbamazepine is medicinally used for the treatment of temporal and grand mal seizures and as antiepileptic drug. It is remarkably specific for trigeminal neuralgia and glosso pharyngeal neuralgia. It has comparable electrophysiological effects on the heart as phenytoin and is occasionally used to alleviate symptoms of diabetic neuropathy¹. Electrochemical reduction of the hydrohalide addition derivatives of carbamazepine has been studied by Duennbier². This study was employed for analytical characterisation of the drug and in process control of the production of these addition compounds.

Results and Discussion

Cyclic voltammograms and differential pulse polarograms were obtained for carbamazepine in the pH range 4.0–10.0. Quasi-reversibly poised cathodic and anodic peaks were obtained in all the media studied. With increase of scan rate the CV profiles approach reversibility while at lower scan rates they deviated from reversibility showing quasi-reversible nature. Typical cyclic voltammograms obtained in carbonate buffer of pH

Plane *abcd* contains both the nitrogens and the carbonyl group and cuts half way through 10,11 C=C bond. *qpr* is the dihedral angle, θ , between the two benzene planes.

10.0 at two scan rates are shown in Fig. 1. In more acidic media of pH < 4.00, the peaks were not obtained properly due to their merging with buffer discharge. The quasi-reversible nature of the redox couple was evident from the large ΔE_p of its cathodic and anodic peak potentials. The number of electrons involved in the reduction process was calculated to be two from differential pulse polarogram through the equation^{5,6},

$$\Delta W_{1/2} = 90.40/n \text{ mV} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta W_{1/2}$ is half peak width, and n the number of electrons. The fact that $n = 2$ was further confirmed by controlled potential coulometry per-

Fig 1 (a) Cyclic voltammogram of 1 at $v = 100 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$, (b) $v = 1000 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$, (c) differential pulse polarogram of 1 (scan rate = 5 mV s^{-1} , $\Delta E = 25 \text{ mV}$, $\Delta t = 56.7 \text{ ms}$, drop time, $t = 1 \text{ s}$).

formed at a potential sufficiently cathodic to the E_{pc} value. The quasi-reversible nature of the reduction process at lower scan rate was also supported by the shift of the cathodic peak potential towards more negative values with increase of concentration. The electrode process was observed to be diffusion-controlled as suggested by the linearity of the plots of peak current vs square root of the scan rate passing through the origin at moderate scan rates. However, when the scan rate is increased to the order of 500 mV/s and more, the $i_{pc}/v^{1/2}$ decreases suggesting the involvement of an EC mechanism.

The diffusion coefficient values at room temperature were evaluated by cyclic voltammetric and differential pulse polarographic techniques employing the equations,⁷

$$i_p = 3.01 \times 10^5 n (\alpha n_a)^{1/2} AD^{1/2} C v^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{and } (\delta_1)_{\max} = \left[\frac{n F A D^{1/2} C}{\pi^{1/2} \Delta t^{1/2}} \right] \left(\frac{1 - \sigma}{1 + \sigma} \right) \quad (3)$$

respectively, where i_p and $(\delta_1)_{\max}$ are peak currents in the voltammograms in μA , n is the number of electrons involved in the electroreduction, A the area of the electrode in cm^2 , D the diffusion coefficient in cm^2/s , C the bulk concentration in mM , v the scan rate in mV/s , Δt the pulse duration in s , and $\sigma = \exp(nF(\Delta E)/2RT)$, where ΔE is the pulse height in mV , and F , R and T have their usual significance.

The compound has two reducible sites in protic solvents (i) the stilbene based ethylenic double bond and (ii) the amide's CO double bond. The benzene rings can not be reduced in the potential range investigated. Amide CO group is very resistant to electroreduction within -2.0 V vs Ag/AgCl . Pure ethylene is also very stable. When it is in extended conjugation with a benzene ring as in stilbene the reduction potential shifts anodically. The *trans*-stilbene, where the ethylenic link is in extended conjugation with two coplanar benzene rings favoured by Hückel's $(4n + 2)\pi$ electron aromaticity, has a standard reduction potential of -1.70 V (vs Ag/AgCl). However, *cis*-stilbene is vulnerable for reduction due to the strain at the ethylenic double bond caused by the steric factors contributed by the 2,2'-benzene hydrogens. Hence the standard reduction potential of *cis*-stilbene shifts more anodically to -1.60 V (vs Ag/AgCl). The stilbenic, 10,11 C=C in carbamazepine is further destabilised by the presence of a puckered seven-membered azepine heterocyclic ring (1).

The fact that the observed cathodic CV peak for the carbamazepine is very close to -1.60 V , suggests that the reduction is effected at the stilbenic double bond. The solution, after prolonged constant potential electrolysis at -1.80 V vs Ag/AgCl at mercury pool working electrode has given a spectrum different from what the pre-electrolysis solution did. Further, the post-electrolysis uv spectrum resembles considerably the spectrum of imipramine which is in structural resemblance to that of 10,11-dihydrocarbamazepine. The quasi-reversibility at low scan rates, approaching a near reversible behaviour at

high scan rates, suggests an EC mechanism for the electroreduction. The involvement of an EC mechanism for the electrochemistry of carbamazepine is supported by other diagnostic criteria viz. (i) at lower scan rates the i_{pc}/i_{pa} ratio is less than 1, but asymptotically approaches 1 as the scan rate is enhanced, (ii) at higher scan rates i_{pc} vs $v^{1/2}$ deviates from linearity with a concavity facing the x -axis ($v^{1/2}$ axis) and (iii) the E_{pc} shifts cathodically with a step of about 15 mV for every 10-fold increase in the scan rate⁵.

Based on the above observations, a tentative EC mechanism is proposed as in Scheme 1 for the electrochemical behaviour of carbamazepine in aqueous media. Forms A and B comprise a reversible redox couple whereas forms A and C a quasi-reversible one. Forms B, C and D are conformational isomers of 10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenz[*b,f*]azepine-5-carboxamide which is conveniently referred to as 10,11-dihydrocarbamazepine. Correlation of the sequences of Scheme 1 with the cyclic voltammetric results at varying scan rate, v , switching potential, E_{λ} and pH, is reasonable. The conclusions drawn in favour of Scheme 1 are further supported by the ultraviolet spectral monitoring and CV studies of structurally comparable imipramine.

At low scan rates there is enough duration for the reduced product B to isomerise to conformation C due to latter's higher stability. Hence, oxidation of C to A in the reverse scan is relatively difficult as it would need to pass through an intermediate stage in form B. When the scan rate is very fast and E_{λ} is not very far away from E_{pc} , the electrode assumes E_{pa} faster than

Scheme 1

the conformational isomeric conversion of B to C leaving considerable concentration of B at the electrode surface resulting in a reversible CV pattern. Anodic CV scan of the electrolysed solution starting at an initial potential of -1.80 V vs Ag/AgCl did not result in any anodic peak even upto -0.2 V vs Ag/AgCl confirming the conformational free energy potential well for form C in form D. The fact that the hydrogenated (electroreduced) carbamazepine, i.e. 10,11-dihydro-5-carboxamide finally destines into the stable electroinactive conformational isomer D is proved by the total disappearance of anodic peak during the reverse scan after holding the potential scan at E_{λ} for nearly 10 min.

Based on the numerical analytical solutions reported by Nicholson and Shain, the confor-

TABLE 1—ELECTROCHEMICAL DATA OF CARBAMAZEPINE*

Sl no	Supporting electrolyte	Cyclic voltammetry ^a				Differential pulse polarography		
		$-E_{pc}$ V	i_{pc} μA	$D \times 10^3$ $cm^2 s^{-1}$	k_f s^{-1}	$-E_p$ V	$(\delta)_{\max}$ μA	$D \times 10^3$ $cm^2 s^{-1}$
1	Acetate buffer of pH 5.0	1.59	0.64	38.30	1.82	1.57	2.4	33.48
2	0.08 M KCl solution	1.60	0.35	35.30	1.84	1.58	2.0	32.41
3	Ammonia buffer of pH 8.60	1.57	0.31	36.79	1.84	1.55	1.3	31.10
4	Carbonate buffer of pH 10.0	1.60	0.42	38.26	1.84	1.59	2.0	32.30

* At 2×10^{-3} M ^a E_{pc} and i_{pc} measured at $n = 100$ mV s⁻¹ and D at $v = 1000$ mV s⁻¹. ^b $\Delta E = 25$ mV and $\Delta t = 56.7$ ms

mational isomerisation rate constant k_f for the following-reaction, i.e. the conversion of B to C is evaluated^{5,8,9}. The method of evaluating the forward rate constant for the following-reactions is briefly outlined here. This method is applicable for any electron transfer process which is close to reversibility at higher scan rates and loses reversibility due to an irreversible following-chemical reaction. For such mechanism the cathodic peak potential, E_{pc} is given by

$$E_{pc} = E_{1/2} - 0.780 (RT/nF) + (RT/2 nF) \ln \lambda \quad (4)$$

where $E_{1/2}$ is the polarographic half-wave potential and λ is a function of rate constant k_f and scan rate v as

$$\lambda = k_f(RT/nFv) \quad (5)$$

A working curve, developed by Nicholson and Shain through numerical methods and plotted as $n(E_{pc} - E_{1/2})$ vs $\log \lambda$ is available⁵. A set of $n(E_{pc} - E_{1/2})$ was calculated from the CV profiles of carbamazepine at different scan rates while obtaining the $E_{1/2}$ value from the CV profile at a high scan rate or from the DPP. Intrapolation of these data from the working curve gave the corresponding $\log \lambda$ values from which, by substituting the v values were the k_f values finally evaluated. The k_f values are, as expected for a following-chemical reactions, are independent of scan rate. The k_f values are obviously rather large and can be attributed to the fact that the chemical reaction proposed (Scheme 1) is a simple unimolecular conformational isomerisation with a lower activation energy. The average k_f values thus obtained, at various pH's are collected in Table 1.

Drug assaying : Carbamazepine (100 mg) is commercially available in the market from several pharmaceutical firms under different trade names. Carbamazepine is estimated successfully employing differential pulse polarographic technique, adopting 'calibration method'. The assay of the drug in a few commercial samples is given in Table 2.

Experimental

Carbamazepine, extracted from commercial samples, was recrystallised from ethanol. The purity of the sample was checked : m.p. 189–191° (lit.³

191–192°) (Found : C, 76.77; H, 5.27; N, 11.64. $C_{15}H_{12}N_2O$ calcd. for : C, 76.17; H, 5.07; N, 11.84%). A.R. grade chemicals were used throughout. Stock aqueous solution of 0.01 M carbamazepine was prepared by first dissolving it in a minimum quantity of absolute ethanol made up to 100 ml with double distilled water. The test solution was made by pipetting out 1 ml of the stock solution and 4 ml of the supporting electrolyte (buffer) into the electrochemical cell. The test solution was purged with purified nitrogen gas to remove the dissolved oxygen and then voltammograms were recorded.

TABLE 2—ASSAY OF CARBAMAZEPINE BY DIFFERENTIAL PULSE POLAROGRAPHIC TECHNIQUE IN CARBONATE BUFFER OF pH 10.00

Sample no.	Amount labelled mg	Amount recovered as analysed mg	Recovery %
1	100	99.32	99.32
2	100	99.64	99.64
3	100	99.35	99.35
4	100	98.46	98.46

Cyclic voltammograms and differential pulse polarograms were recorded on a PARC 264 A3 polarographic analyzer/stripping voltammeter equipped with PARC 303A static mercury drop electrode assembly and PARC RE 0150 X-Y recorder. The three-electrode cell comprised of a working electrode in a hanging mercury drop electrode (in case of cyclic voltammetry) and dropping mercury electrode (in case of differential pulse polarography) of area 0.0096 cm², platinum wire counter electrode and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode. An Elico LI 120 pH meter was used. Coulometry and controlled potential electrolysis were carried out on a mercury pool working electrode with the other two counter and reference electrodes, using the same electrochemical set-up.

The uv spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer using thermostated quartz cells of 1 cm path length. The C, H and N analysis was carried out on a Carlo-Erba EA 1108 analyzer equipped with DP-200 data processor. The buffers of pH 4.0, 5.0, 8.6 and 10.0 were made following the literature procedures⁴. Molecular conformational arguments were

discerned by constructing molecular models using Z 11, 965-2 Cochranes molecular model kit supplied by Aldrich,

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